

ASTRAL

All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, ProfiTable and Resilient AquacuLture

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Dedication to Professor Thierry Chopin

Professor Thierry Chopin, passed away on July 18 2024. Renowned for his work in the field of aquaculture, Professor Chopin's dedication has left an indelible mark on both the academic world and his pioneering work on Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA).

Throughout his distinguished career, Professor Chopin made significant contributions to the sustainable development of aquaculture. His innovative research in IMTA, involving the cultivation of multiple, complementary species such as salmon, mussels, and seaweed, transformed traditional aquaculture practices. This approach not only enhanced environmental sustainability but also improved economic viability by creating balanced ecosystems that mimic natural interactions. Professor Chopin's efforts earned him international recognition and respect, establishing him as a leading authority in the field.

We had the distinct pleasure of collaborating with him on the ASTRAL project. His countless contributions to the project were evident in his extensive work within WP2 and his invaluable inputs and critique of all the IMTA lab deliverables and outputs. He will be remembered amongst his ASTRAL colleagues for his warmth, kindness and great sense of humour.

Professor Chopin will continue to inspire future generations of scientists and environmentalists. His life's work has made a lasting impact on aquaculture and he will be deeply missed by his colleagues and friends in the sector.

Summary

This catalogue describes the ASTRAL IMTA species of the future. These species have been trialled at the ASTRAL IMTA labs in Scotland, Ireland, Brazil and South Africa and have been identified as the optimal species to be cultivated within each type of system, based on their cultivation performance, resilience, profitability and sustainability. The system types include open water IMTA (Scotland and Ireland); land-based pump ashore IMTA with partial recirculation (South Africa) and recirculating aquaculture system (RAS) using biofloc IMTA (Brazil). The potential for IMTA in Argentina and Nigeria is also described.

1 Introduction

With the knowledge gathered under ASTRAL Tasks 2.1 - 2.5 (Deliverables D2.2 – 2.5, D2.8), ASTRAL has developed a “Species for the future” catalogue, gathering the best IMTA species to be cultivated in each type of ASTRAL IMTA system. These species have been trialled at the ASTRAL IMTA labs in Scotland, Ireland, Brazil and South Africa and have been identified as the optimal species to be cultivated within each type of system. The system types include open water IMTA (Scotland and Ireland); land-based pump ashore IMTA with partial recirculation (South Africa) and recirculating aquaculture system (RAS) using biofloc IMTA (Brazil). The potential for IMTA in Argentina and Nigeria is also described. These species are identified based on their cultivation performance, resilience, profitability and sustainability. For this catalogue, contributions are included from WP4 (sustainability and circularity), WP5 (climate) and WP6 (business models, socio-economics).

[Note: each chapter can be read as an individual catalogue, common items of information are repeated across some chapters.]

2 Open water IMTA

IMTA production can be carried out in several differing aquaculture systems. Open water IMTA, as carried out in the ASTRAL project in IMTA lab Ireland and IMTA lab Scotland refers to species production at sea with mooring structures in place to anchor the cultivation structures to the seabed. This type of system is continuously exposed to prevailing environmental conditions, including wind and wave action.

Production methods for this type of IMTA system and the ASTRAL IMTA open water species can be found in detail in D2.8 ASTRAL Production Manuals.

Open water IMTA depicting potential species

Co-cultivation of seaweed and shellfish species at IMTA Lab Scotland (©SAMS).

2.1 Species

Astral open water species of the future

Common name	Latin name	Role in IMTA
Atlantic salmon	<i>Salmo salar</i>	Fed species
Winged kelp	<i>Alaria esculenta</i>	Extractive Species
Sugar kelp	<i>Saccharina latissima</i>	Extractive Species
Furbelows	<i>Saccorhiza polyschides</i>	Extractive Species
King scallop	<i>Pecten maximus</i>	Extractive Species
European flat oyster	<i>Ostrea edulis</i>	Extractive Species
Purple sea urchin	<i>Paracentrotus lividus</i>	Extractive Species

2.2 Source

Sources and production landscape for open water IMTA species in Europe.

	<i>Salmo salar</i>	<i>Alaria esculenta</i>	<i>Saccharina latissima</i>	<i>Saccorhiza polyschides</i>	<i>Ostrea edulis</i>	<i>Paracentrotus lividus</i>	<i>Pecten maximus</i>
Is there a source or hatchery for juveniles or seed?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Research only	Limited
Is it possible to culture these species from a regulatory standpoint?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

2.3 Culturing

ASTRAL D2.8 contains details of the culturing methods for all the open water species.

2.3.1 Salmon

Atlantic salmon *Salmo salar*

Life cycle of farmed Atlantic salmon. ©Marine Institute

Atlantic salmon are the fed species in this open water IMTA system.

The production of Atlantic salmon is well documented and the rearing of salmon in IMTA cultivation does not differ from that of monoculture methods or production cycles.

References for the production of Atlantic salmon:

- The Farmed Salmonid Handbook –
[The Farmed Salmonid Handbook | Fish Health Unit](#)
- Salmon Farming Industry Handbook 2023
<https://mowi.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/2023-Salmon-Farming-Industry-Handbook-2023.pdf>

2.3.2 Seaweed

Life cycle of ASTRAL seaweed species. ©Marine Institute & SAMS

Alaria esculenta, *Saccharina latissima* and *Saccorhiza polyschides* growth on cultivation lines.

- Brown macroalgae such as kelp species are typically grown on longlines deployed horizontally and parallel to the predominant current flow at site.
- Fertile seaweed material is sourced locally, followed by spore release and seed bulk culture in designated hatcheries.
- Seeding begins with the seaweed cultures being seeded onto reels of twine (= carrier material) maintained under controlled light and nutrient conditions for 4-6 weeks before deployment onto cultivation lines for grow-out at sea in early Autumn.
- Site selection is critical with moderate wave exposure, good current flow and thus nutrient supply, and limited freshwater input from land being generally ideal for kelp species with some species-specific preferences.
- Regular monitoring of environmental cultivation conditions, seaweed growth, and grow-out infrastructure is advised, involving seaweed sampling for biomass yields and composition, assessing line integrity and position (line tension and buoying-up to maintain seaweed at optimal growing depth).
- Seaweed harvest season occurs from in early Spring to early Summer; exact harvest time depends on the intended application and requirements of the product (early season harvest for food/feed applications – late season harvest for high-quantity application such as biofuel).
- Seaweed harvest is performed either manually or fully automated, followed by drying (kelp contains up to 90 % water) and additional down-stream processing for most products.

2.3.3 Urchin

Purple Sea Urchin *Paracentrotus lividus*

Production cycle of farmed sea urchin¹. ©Marine Institute

¹ Formery et al (2022). Developmental atlas of the indirect-developing sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus*: From fertilization to juvenile stages. *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology* 10.

- Juvenile urchin have been successfully cultivated in adapted shellfish growing structures such as HDPE baskets.
- Depending on the size of growing structures, a stocking density should be accounted for (approximately 30 urchin per unit). As urchin grow, this density may need to be reduced.
- Growing baskets should be submerged at least 2 metres in depth and hung from longlines next to salmon cages.
- Urchin can be feed on a variety of seaweed diets, a mix of kelp species can be used. Baskets should be filled with seaweed to help cushion urchin during periods of intense hydrodynamics.
- To monitor urchin growth, the diameter of each urchin can be measured every two weeks when stocking baskets with feed, using a set of callipers.
- Growth to harvest can take 3-4 years. The minimum size in diameter for urchin harvest is 5-6 cm, ensuring urchin have reached reproductive maturity.

2.3.4 Oyster

Native oyster *Ostrea edulis*

Production cycle of *Ostrea edulis*. ©Marine Institute

- The European flat oyster *Ostrea edulis* is of ecological and commercial value and received increasing attention for restorative aquaculture, to replenish diminished wild populations, for its commercial value and for being considered a luxury seafood item in many regions.
- *Ostrea edulis* is prone to contracting diseases (mainly Bonamiosis and Marteilirosis) affecting its growth and survival and hindering the upscaling of commercial production. Susceptibility to disease is mainly determined by the oyster's life stage and exposure to environmental stressors e.g. prolonged heat stress.
- Cultivation commonly takes place in the intertidal area with oyster holding equipment (bags, rags, baskets) being deployed on long trestle tables reaching into the water. Subtidal i.e. suspended cultivation is increasingly employed with oysters being continuously submerged in the water and thus less likely to experience heat stress and reducing susceptibility to diseases.
- Seed oysters can be sourced naturally with spat settling onto deployed collectors, or, from certified hatcheries at 5-6 mm shell height.
- Oysters require 3-4 years to reach harvest size of ≥ 70 mm shell height, depending on site location and prevailing environmental conditions. During grow-out, holding structures are regularly inspected and cleaned from on growing epifauna and -flora limiting water flow. Oysters are also continuously graded and re-deployed by size minimising overcrowding and facilitating good growth.
- Oysters are predominantly sold as live in-shell product and to a lesser extent as smoked and/or canned oyster meat.

2.3.5 Scallop

King scallop *Pecten maximus*

Production cycle of *Pecten maximus*. ©Marine Institute

- European scallop production is dominated by king scallop *Pecten maximus*, and to a lesser extent queen scallop *Aequipecten opercularis*, including wild capture fishery and commercial cultivation.
- For commercial culture, scallop spat naturally settles onto deployed collectors and is transferred to grow-out structures at 20-33mm shell height. Modular grow-out structures such as lantern nets or stacked nestier trays are used and suspended from longlines or floating rafts.
- As for other contained species e.g. oysters, grow-out structures are regularly assessed for damage and cleaned from biofouling for optimal water flow and thus food supply.
- Scallops are continuously graded by size and deployed in small stocking densities to facilitate growth and limit competition for space and food resources.
- Site selection is important with scallops requiring low to moderate current flows, stable full-strength salinity and well oxygenated water for growth and survival.
- Scallops can reach harvest size of ≥ 90 mm shell height after 3 years of cultivation at sea, with the exact duration depending on the required product weight and prevailing environmental as well as cultivation conditions.
- Scallops are mainly sold as in-shell product or separated into meat (adductor muscle and gonad) and emptied shells with the latter often being used for ornamental purposes.

2.4 Sustainability

From a cradle to farm-gate perspective the integration of seaweed, urchin and oysters into the salmon farming, contributes to reduce the carbon footprint and eutrophication impacts. Life cycle assessment (LCA) results (D4.3) reveals that the production of 1 kg of fresh weight biomass in IMTA systems potentially reduces by 6.5% the impacts on the climate change, while the marine eutrophication is mitigated by 27.5%. Extractive species reduce the overall feed needed per unit of biomass production. Infrastructure in IMTA plays a major role in the environmental footprint, and polypropylene and steel elements need attention to ensure a higher sustainability. Improving the rearing system infrastructure for the low trophic species can increase the culture surface area and ultimately the area for bioremediation.

When seaweed, king scallops, oysters, and sea urchins are integrated together, the same LCA study indicated that the cultivation phase has a positive effect on the environment, reducing negative impacts of eutrophication through nutrient uptake (N and P). An appropriate selection of infrastructure elements, with less replacements and better life expectancy can notably improve the overall environmental profile for low trophic species cultivation.

Under a circularity perspective, seaweeds, sea urchins and oysters promote nutrient recycling (link to eutrophication mitigation and ecosystem services), while making the system more efficient in terms of energy use per unit of biomass harvested (D4.2). A dedicated analysis on the circularity of infrastructure materials revealed that the integrated cultivation of *Alaria esculenta*, *Saccharina latissima*, *Ostrea edulis* and *Pecten maximus*, with a theoretical replacement of conventional ropes with coconut biobased ropes, would increase the material circularity indicator more than 42%, compared to monoculture -seaweed- cultivation. In terms of bioremediation: 7.71%, 12.08% and 2.63 % of N, P and C were mitigated respectively when seaweed, sea urchin and oyster were integrated with salmon farming.

2.5 Market, financial feasibility and profitability, and socio-economics

- Offshore system reducing the pollution risk from coastal areas and optimising biomass production: higher profitability for the producer.
- Importance of the value proposition in the business model: high quality product.
- A growing demand for sustainable seafood: high market potential, especially for oysters for the European market.
- High quality of products and efficient traceability is a key for the value proposition.
- Growing social appeal for certified and environmentally-friendly products: especially in the northern hemisphere --> Economical interest in labelling products.
- Possible conflicts for space with other activities (tourism sector, fishing).
- High investment needed for robust equipment that can withstand the elements (wind, swell, salinity, etc.).
- Complex and long regulatory process for setting up aquaculture farms.
- Availability of juveniles is essential in the value chain: this is an important element to factor into costs if there is an external need.
- Main costs: human resources and R&D.
- Once capital costs are established, fixed cost are modest.
- High demand in skilled human resources and for technological skills.
- Lack of data and feedback on IMTA: a barrier to public and private investors.

2.6 Resilience to future impacts

ASTRAL has defined resilience as follows:

'The capacity of the cultured species to respond to, resist, adapt and recover from changes in the external environment such as biotic (biological) and abiotic (physical and chemical) stress, climate change and disease'

Climate change trends have been assessed for all Large Marine Ecosystems (LMEs) in the Atlantic Ocean as part of ASTRAL Deliverable 5.1². The LME surrounding the IMTA sites in Ireland and Scotland (the Celtic-Biscay Shelf) is found to be the most vulnerable to climate change in terms of oxygen as well as a strong increase in pCO₂ and a corresponding strong decline in surface pH during the period 1980-2021. In this region there has also been a strong increase in sea surface temperature as well as occurrences of marine heat waves³, which is expected to continue. Currently, none of the species investigated at the IMTA sites in Ireland and Scotland are exposed to environmental conditions outside of their tolerance range. Open water IMTAs are most vulnerable to climate change, disease, and other stressors because they are open to their environment. Severe weather events, changes in wind patterns and ocean currents, changes in stratification due to changing glacier and/or river run-off will thus be a stress factor for the farmed species. These factors are also risk factors associated with harmful algae bloom events.

² <https://zenodo.org/records/10848745>

³ Berthou, S., Renshaw, R., Smyth, T. et al. (2024) Exceptional atmospheric conditions in June 2023 generated a northwest European marine heatwave which contributed to breaking land temperature records. *Commun Earth Environ* 5, 287. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-024-01413-8>

Optimal (in green) and tolerance ranges (blue arrow ends) of some of the water quality parameters for key ASTRAL cultivated species. *Salmo salar* dissolved oxygen tolerance range is 70-100% relative to temperature and pH. Figure taken from ASTRAL Deliverable 5.5⁴**

⁴ ASTRAL D5.5 ASTRAL monitoring programme and recommendations for dedicated monitoring at IMTA labs

3 Land based pump ashore system

IMTA production can be carried out in several differing aquaculture systems. Land based pump ashore systems, as carried out in the ASTRAL project in IMTA lab South Africa, refers to species production in land raceways and paddle raceways. Production methods and details of the production system for this type of IMTA system can be found in detail in the D2.8 ASTRAL Production Manual.

Land-based pump ashore IMTA system to produce abalone (*Haliotis midae*) and seaweed (*Ulva lacinulata*) at Buffeljags Abalone Farm. (a) Aerial photograph of the modular abalone-Ulva IMTA (©Viking Aquaculture). (b) IMTA process in a single abalone-Ulva cluster (©Brett Macey).

3.1 Species

Astral land-based pump ashore species of the future

Common name	Latin name	Role in IMTA
Abalone	<i>Haliotis midae</i>	Fed species
Sea lettuce	<i>Ulva lacinulata</i>	Extractive species
Collector sea urchin	<i>Tripneustes gratilla</i>	Fed species
Cape sea urchin	<i>Parechinus angulosus</i>	Novel (fed) species

3.2 Source

Sources and production landscape for land-based pump ashore IMTA species.

Species	<i>Haliotis midae</i>	<i>Tripneustes gratilla</i>	<i>Ulva lacinulata</i>	<i>Parechinus angulosus</i>
Is there a source or hatchery for juveniles or seed?	✓	✓	✓	Research only
Is it possible to culture these species from a regulatory standpoint?	✓	✓	✓	✓

3.3 Culturing

ASTRAL D2.8 contains details of the culturing methods for all the open water species.

3.3.1 Abalone

South African abalone *Haliotis midae* are grown in land-based pump ashore systems integrated with the green seaweed *Ulva lacinulata* (A). Juvenile abalone are typically housed under cones in the hatchery systems (B), whereas adults are housed in baskets on the grow-out platforms (C) and fed IMTA grown *Ulva* from the seaweed paddle raceways (D). (©Viking & UCT)

Production cycle of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae*. ©DFFE & UCT.

- The South African abalone (*Haliotis midae*) is cultivated in land-based pump-ashore partially (50%) recirculating aquaculture systems integrated with the green seaweed *Ulva lacinulata*
- Abalone are grown in baskets (20 baskets.raceway⁻¹ stocked at ca. 10kg.basket⁻¹) suspended in fiberglass raceways and are fed a mixed diet of formulated feed, kelp (*Ecklonia maxima*) and IMTA grown *U. lacinulata*
- Optimal environmental ranges for growth of *H. midae* in land-based systems are: temperature 12-20°C; salinity 30-25psu; dissolved oxygen >90% (7-8mg.L⁻¹); pH 7.7-8.2; free ammonia nitrogen (FAN) < 7.5µg.L⁻¹
- Effluent water leaving abalone tanks is bioremediated by seaweed grown in adjacent *Ulva* paddle-raceways and bioremediated water is returned to abalone raceways after mixing with 50% fresh seawater from the adjacent ocean
- Juveniles are produced in a hatchery on-site from conditioned broodstock animals and transferred to the grow-out platforms after 9-10 months (16-18mm shell length).
- The diet of juvenile abalone (< 3 mm shell length) can be supplemented with faecal matter from the Cape sea urchin (*Parechinus angulosus*) to improve growth and health of the early juvenile stages (see ASTRAL deliverable 2.4 for more details).
- Grow-out takes 2-4 years to produce abalone which are ca. 100-140 mm in size
- Cultured abalone are traded as either live, frozen, dried, or canned products and predominantly exported to the Far East.

3.3.2 Sea urchin

Collector sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* grown in a land-based raceway system suspended in shallow baskets (A). Urchins are often fed the green seaweed *Ulva lacinulata* (B) for most of the production cycle and finished off with a formulated feed to bulk gonads (C) prior to harvest. (©John Bolton)

Production cycle of the collector sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*. ©UCT & DFFE.

- The collector sea urchin (*Tripneustes gratilla*) is cultivated in land-based pump-ashore partially (90%) recirculating aquaculture systems integrated with the green seaweed *Ulva lacunculata*
- Urchins are grown in baskets (20 baskets.raceway⁻¹ stocked at ca. 8kg.basket⁻¹) during the grow-out phase of production, suspended in fiberglass raceways
- Optimal environmental ranges for growth of *T. gratilla* in land-based systems are: temperature 24-28°C; salinity 35psu; dissolved oxygen >90% (>6mg.L⁻¹); pH 8.0-8.2; free ammonia nitrogen (FAN) < 16µg.L⁻¹
- Effluent water leaving urchin tanks is bioremediated by seaweed grown in adjacent *Ulva* paddle-raceways and bioremediated water is returned to urchin raceways after mixing with 10% fresh seawater from the adjacent ocean
- Juveniles are produced in a hatchery on-site from conditioned broodstock animals and transferred to the grow-out platforms after 2-3 months (5-10mm test diameter)
- Somatic growth phase during grow-out takes 6-7 months, whereas the gonad enhancement phase takes another 3-4 months to bulk gonads prior to marketing (55-60mm test diameter)
- High quality gonads with a bright and firm yellow or orange appearance are generally exported as fresh product (harvested or as whole urchins), whereas lower quality products are processed for market by baking, freezing, steaming and salting.

3.4 Sustainability

From a cradle to gate perspective, the integrated urchin-*Ulva* system clearly outperforms monoculture in terms of environmental performance. The recirculation significantly enhances the bioremediation of organic matter and nutrients. Moreover, *Ulva* biomass reduces the reliance on formulated feed and is employed as a direct feed source for sea urchins on-site. In the context of the LCA study (D4.3⁵), results show that *Ulva* effectively assimilates approximately 84% of the dissolved nitrogen that is released by the sea urchins, reducing the impact of eutrophication. The same study evidences reduced energy consumption in an integrated urchin-*Ulva* system, which improves the overall environmental footprint: 38.45% reduction in climate change impacts and a reduction up to 49% in eutrophication. The abalone-*Ulva* system showed benefits in terms of bioremediation as the incorporation of macroalgae contributes notably to the absorption of nutrients emitted by abalone. Additionally, abalone-*Ulva* is a sustainable system that reduces the dependence on the pumping of fresh seawater, contributing to energy efficiency. Finally, the integrated abalone-*Ulva* system promotes the reduction of Food Conversion Ratio (FCR) and linearity of feed composition when abalone is fed with the harvested *Ulva*.

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/10848703>

3.5 Market, financial feasibility and profitability, and socio-economics

- High amount of investment: key upstream partners are investors or public funders / importance of political support in setting up farms / availabilities of land
- Saving production costs and dependency: recirculation is decreasing water pumping costs and electricity requirements
- Land based system highly dependent on external factors including land availabilities and resource availabilities (seawater and wild seaweed for example)
- Main costs: human resources and production costs, including transport costs for urchins (air freight)
- Urchins: 100% export market for Asia
- Social perception of land based aquaculture : highly dependent on the localisation
- Consistency of the production of sea urchins: year-round production possible with a land-based system
- Modular, land-based tank system: mitigate disease spread and HAB risk reduction, system resistance and controlled interaction system
- Urchins: New high-valued low-trophic aquaculture species from South Africa and emerging species with high market value and with high demand in Asia (Japan 80%)
- High quality of products (especially urchins and the gonads) thanks to an efficient traceability is a key for the value proposition

3.6 Resilience to future impacts

ASTRAL has defined resilience as follows:

'The capacity of the cultured species to respond to, resist, adapt and recover from changes in the external environment such as biotic (biological) and abiotic (physical and chemical) stress, climate change and disease'

In terms of climate change trends, the LME adjacent to the IMTA site in South Africa has experienced a moderate long-term warming (1957-2020), and a deceleration in warming for the period 1980-2020. A decreasing trend in oxygen was also identified during the period 1957-2020, with a decline in pH between 1980 and 2021. Land-based IMTA systems with partial, or full, recirculation are less vulnerable to environmental changes than open water systems since they have a certain level of control over some of the physical and chemical variables within a production system, and provide some protection from the ambient environment. However, such systems are still vulnerable to stress from influx of urban wastewater, pollution (including plastics) pathogens, and the degree of control depends on the extent of recirculation as well as on the location of the IMTA production system. Harmful Algal Bloom events are increasing along this coastline, and the ability of these partially recirculated IMTA systems to switch to 100% recirculation for short periods (see D2.4) can partially mitigate risks from HABs.

Optimal (in green) and tolerance ranges (blue arrow ends) of some of the water quality parameters for key ASTRAL cultivated species. ***Salmo salar* dissolved oxygen tolerance range is 70-100% relative to temperature and pH. Figure taken from ASTRAL Deliverable 5.5⁶

⁶ ASTRAL D5.5 ASTRAL monitoring programme and recommendations for dedicated monitoring at IMTA labs

4 Land based – RAS with Biofloc

IMTA production can be carried out in several differing aquaculture systems. The Recirculating Aquaculture System (RAS) with Biofloc, as carried out in the ASTRAL project in IMTA lab Brazil, refers to species production in a land-based recirculating aquaculture system (RAS). Production methods and details of the production system for this type of IMTA can be found in detail in D2.8 ASTRAL Production Manuals.

Schematic of the multitrophic system used at the Federal University of Rio Grande, where water recirculates between different tanks.

4.1 Species

RAS with Biofloc species of the future

Common name	Latin name	Role in IMTA
White shrimp	<i>Penaeus vannamei</i>	Fed species
Tilapia	<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	Fed species
Native oyster	<i>Crassostrea tulipa</i> (formerly <i>Crassostrea gasar</i>)	Extractive species
Seaweed	<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	Extractive species
Sea asparagus	<i>Salicornia neei</i>	Extractive species

4.2 Source

Sources and production landscape for RAS with Biofloc IMTA species.

Species	<i>Penaeus vannamei</i>	<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	<i>Crassostrea tulipa</i>	<i>Salicornia neei</i>	<i>Ulva lactuca</i>
Is there a source or hatchery for juveniles or seed?	✓	✓	✓	Research	✓
Is it possible to culture these species from a regulatory standpoint?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

4.3 Culturing

ASTRAL D2.8 contains details of the culturing methods for all the open water species.

4.3.1 Shrimp

Marine shrimp produced in the multi-trophic system.

Marine shrimp production cycle consisting of a ca. 1 month hatchery phase followed by a 1 month nursery phase and 3 months grow-out phase.

- Shrimp is cultivated in biofloc system in high densities (350-450 ind/m²)
- No water renewal is required during the cycle
- The FCR (1.3 to 1.6) is reduced considering the animal density
- Survival varies between 85% and 95%
- The microorganisms present in the biofloc are responsible to maintaining the water quality and food supplementation
- The BFT system does not generate effluents
- Shrimp production is 20 times higher than observed in conventional systems
- The biofloc formation occurs from organic (molasses or dextrose) or inorganic (carbonates) fertilization.
- The BFT system requires intense aeration for 24 hours
- The ideal temperature is between 28 and 31 °C
- Total suspended solids must be below 350 mg/L
- The system works better in salinities greater than 15

4.3.2 Tilapia

Tilapia produced in the integrated system with marine shrimp, oysters, seaweeds and halophytes.

Tilapia production cycle consisting of a ca. 1-2 month hatchery phase followed by a 1-2 month nursery phase and 4-5 months grow-out phase.

- Tilapia produced in salinity between 15 and 20 has the best price on the market, compared to those produced in fresh water
- The system works best in salinities between 15 and 20
- Densities close to 30 ind/m³ present better animal performance and maintenance of water quality
- FCR ranges between 0.5 and 0.7 in the IMTA system with bioflocs
- Tilapia consume bioflocs and control the system's solid concentrations, reducing the FCR

4.3.3 Oyster

Native oysters (*Crassostrea tulipa*) produced in the multitrophic system.

Oyster production cycle consisting of a ca. 1 month hatchery phase followed by a 2-3 weeks settling phase and 8-10 months grow-out phase.

- Oysters, even though they are filter feeders, do not play a relevant role in the biofloc consumption in the IMTA system
- Even though it is a Brazilian native species, temperatures above 27°C affect the survival of animals
- The best growth and survival performances were observed at TSS concentrations below 250 mg/L

4.3.4 Sea Asparagus

Production of *Salicornia neii* integrated to shrimp, tilapia, oyster and seaweed

- Sea asparagus grows well in the IMTA system, helping to reduce nitrate and phosphate concentrations
- There is no established market in Brazil yet, but with potential for food and pharmaceutical use
- Harvests every 15 days during spring and summer

4.3.5 *Ulva lactuca*

Sea Lettuce (*Ulva lactuca*) produced in the Brazilian IMTA system

- Macroalgae consume nutrients accumulated in the IMTA system, reducing phosphate by more than 75% and nitrate by 22%
- They must be positioned on the surface of the tank (10 cm) to make better use of the light, as bioflocs reduce light penetration
- Temperatures above 28°C affect survival and biomass production
- Macroalgae grow best at TSS concentrations less than 250 mg/L

4.4 Sustainability

Shrimp cultivation in a RAS Biofloc system combining tilapia and seaweed, promotes the reduction of 38% and 49% of climate change and eutrophication impacts respectively, resulting in a better environmental profile of the IMTA system compared to shrimp monoculture. Improving the FCR by using BFT and other species also explains the improvement in the environmental performance of IMTA.

Under a circularity perspective the integration of *Ulva* into the shrimp and tilapia system contributes notably to the recycling of P (75.6%) and N (22.3%). Moreover, when fish meal in shrimp diet is substituted by fish meal analogue, the system increases the circularity as the dependency on linear ingredients is reduced.

4.5 Market, financial feasibility and profitability, and socio-economics

- Minimal use of space by pooling equipment and increasing production densities: reducing occupancy and site size / increasing profitability
- Improved productivity with lower amount of feed required lower material and energy needed for feed production and transportation (Astral LCA)
- Recirculation of water reducing the water supply by using it several times: costs reductions
- High dependency on equipment and power supplies: Power outages and equipment failures causing oxygen deficiency leading to mass mortality
- High temperature needs to be maintained: increasing costs and location reliability. High cost of setting up the infrastructure (including greenhouses, tanks, pumps, filtration system and electricity: used for aeration to maintain the dissolved oxygen concentration in water especially for shrimps' production)
- Tilapia/shrimp/oysters for food industry market mainly
- Seaweeds: main market feed ingredients / cosmetics / nutraceuticals
- Improved biosecurity, since there is no water renewal and the environment is more stable in relation to temperature variations (greenhouses), resulting in less exposure to pathogens and less stress.

4.6 Resilience to future impacts

ASTRAL has defined resilience as follows:

'The capacity of the cultured species to respond to, resist, adapt and recover from changes in the external environment such as biotic (biological) and abiotic (physical and chemical) stress, climate change and disease'

In terms of climate change trends, the LME adjacent to the IMTA site in Brazil experienced a sustained moderate warming during two periods (1957-2020 and 1980-2020) and a strong increase in pCO₂ and decline in pH between 1980 to 2021. Yet, it also shows potentially positive trends for the IMTA-system with an increasing trend of O₂ for the period 1957-2020, confirmed by Ito et al. (2017)⁷. As with partially recirculating systems, biofloc systems provide some control over the environmental variables within the system and may also be able to treat or filter some of the water pumped into the system to avoid pathogens and harmful algae. However, in most cases land-based ponds or tanks are exposed to the elements and are sensitive to severe weather events and their changing frequency.

⁷ Ito, Minobe, Long, and Deutsch, 2017: Upper ocean O₂ trends: 1958–2015, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 44, pp. 4214–4223, doi:10.1002/2017GL073613.

Optimal (in green) and tolerance ranges (blue arrow ends) of some of the water quality parameters for key ASTRAL cultivated species. ***Salmo salar* dissolved oxygen tolerance range is 70-100% relative to temperature and pH. Figure taken from ASTRAL Deliverable 5.5⁸

⁸ ASTRAL D5.5 ASTRAL monitoring programme and recommendations for dedicated monitoring at IMTA labs

5 Potential for IMTA in Argentina

The prospective IMTA lab Argentina explored the potential of native species from the Southwest Atlantic Ocean and focused on promoting and developing IMTA in the Beagle Channel and along the Patagonian Region.

Typical landscape of the Beagle Channel with Chilean mountain.

A total of 44 species of fish, crustacean, mollusc, echinoderm, algae, and halophytes native to the Beagle Channel were evaluated to determine their potential for IMTA, selecting four species as best candidates. The first potential IMTA configuration is integrated with whitebait (fed aquaculture) and *sarcocornia* (extractive aquaculture) maintained on land-based semi-closed systems.

Native species to the Beagle Channel for IMTA

Common name	Latin name	Role in IMTA
Whitebait	<i>Galaxias maculatus</i>	Fed aquaculture
Glasswort	<i>Sarcocornia magellanica</i>	Extractive aquaculture
Blue mussel	<i>Mytilus chilensis</i>	Extractive aquaculture
Red sea urchin	<i>Loxechinus albus</i>	Fed aquaculture

5.1 Potential Species and IMTA Systems

5.1.1 Whitebait (*Galaxias maculatus*)

Whitebait (*Galaxias maculatus*)

Whitebait, also known as *puyen chico* in Argentina, *puye* in Chile and *inanga* in Australia, New Zealand, and Tasmania, is the most widespread freshwater fish in the world. Its distribution range in Argentina comprises the Patagonian Region, from 32°S to the Beagle Channel at 55°S. The maximum size of this species in the Beagle Channel has been estimated at 120 mm, with extraordinary records of 155 mm in length.

Whitebait is one of five Galaxiid species commercialised in New Zealand and is highly valued internationally since it is considered a commercial simile of eel alevin. The most common commercialised product is the whole frozen crystalline larvae of 0.3-0.5 g with 4-6 mm length. It is one of the costliest fish on the market in New Zealand, reaching values up to U\$S 154/kg of frozen entire fish. Chile also has a high market demand, commercialised at U\$S 56/kg, with a range price of about U\$S25-100/kg. Whitebait is not a well-known product in Argentina's gastronomic field. However, the fact that it is a product like the European eel (*Anguilla anguilla*) consumed in Europe and Asia means that whitebait has great gastronomic potential and could be focused on consumption by international tourists. Nevertheless, it is not included in the Argentine food code, which makes its traceability difficult and could have little confidence on the part of consumers.

Chile and New Zealand have had several aquaculture programs to develop whitebait farms in the last 4 decades⁹. This species supports high manipulation and low water quality in captivity, facilitating the productive cycle. So far, only land-based systems (open and RAS) have been used. The complete life cycle in captivity has been achieved in 390 days. However, capture-based aquaculture is carried out

⁹ Mardones A, et al. (2008). Cultivation of whitebait (*Galaxias maculatus*) in Chile. *Aquaculture Research* 39: 731-737

since production still depends on eggs obtained by extracting wild broodstock for breeding. The growth cycle may begin with the purchase/capture of crystalline fry, which grows until it reaches sexual maturity. The gametes are obtained by stripping and incubated for 25-30 days in a humidity incubation system. The larvae take around 140 days to reach the juvenile stage, at which time a part of the stock can be harvested, and the rest continue growing until reaching sexual maturity and used for the next productive cycle. This first productive cycle, starting from the capture of wild fry to obtaining eggs, takes approximately 480 days. In comparison, a productive cycle with an already established breeding stock takes 150 - 180 days from the fertilisation of the eggs to the harvest of juveniles.

Productive cycle of whitebait. © CADIC-CONICET.

Since one of the main bottlenecks of whitebait aquaculture is obtaining juveniles, the best strategy could be collecting wild individuals. The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations has recognised this production strategy as capture-based aquaculture. Capture-based aquaculture has certain advantages and disadvantages compared to aquaculture, which controls the complete cycle of the cultured species. To use this production strategy, it is essential to know the state of conservation of the natural populations to avoid any alteration. For this reason, it is recommended that this species be commercialised only through a certification process that shows that the products have come from aquaculture and not from wild populations.

5.1.2 Glasswort (*Sarcocornia magellanica*)

Glasswort (*Sarcocornia magellanica*)

Sarcocornia is a genus of halophytic edible succulent plants that belongs to the Amaranthaceae family. This genus includes 28 species commonly named glasswort, samphire, or just sarcocornia. *Sarcocornia* is distributed worldwide in saline environments, usually salt marshes habitats with low precipitation, tolerating concentrations of up to 40 g/L of salinity. *Sarcocornia magellanica* is an endemic species to southern Argentina and Chile, growing in salt marshes associated with the Atlantic tides. It is a perennial species, allowing partial harvests for several years.

In Patagonia (Chile and Argentina), *Sarcocornia neei* and *S. magellanica* have been historically harvested from natural banks near the seashore. The salt tolerance and the high nutritional value for humans make *Sarcocornia spp.* a halophyte with the potential to be integrated into aquaculture systems with brackish or marine species. This species is also promising to develop aquaculture in the context of climate change and soil and water salinisation, added to the fact that this crop does not require the use of freshwater. *Sarcocornia spp.* have been used in aquaculture for bioremediation of marine fisheries wastewaters¹⁰, in aquaponic systems¹¹, and for production diversification in integrated biofloc systems¹².

Due to their nutritional (fibre, and antioxidant vitamins), organoleptic and medicinal properties, sarcocornia has a high economic potential in various biotechnology sectors and are considered

¹⁰ Beyer CP, et al. (2021). *Sarcocornia neei*: A novel halophyte species for bioremediation of marine aquaculture wastewater and production diversification in integrated systems. *Aquaculture* 543:736971

¹¹ Spradlin A, Saha S (2022). Saline aquaponics: A review of challenges, opportunities, components, and system design. *Aquaculture*, 555:738173

¹² Pinheiro I, et al. (2020). Aquaponic production of *Sarcocornia ambigua* and Pacific white shrimp in biofloc system at different salinities. *Aquaculture* 519:734918

promising gourmet vegetables to be explored in the context of climate change, soil, and water salinisation. *Sarcocornia magellanica* has a high Ca^{++} and Mg^{++} content, good digestibility, high protein content and abundant unsaturated essential fatty acids, giving it the potential for prolonged cholesterol treatments. It has been tested and developed commercially for fresh or dry human consumption, and cultivation possibilities for sheep foraging have been tested in Argentina. The retail value of glasswort in Europe can be estimated by the current values for *Salicornia* at around 12 €/kg. To develop the local market, chefs must promote the use of glasswort through gastronomic courses. Regarding the distrust about the traceability and safety of glasswort, it should be made known that *S. magellanica* was registered in the Argentine Food Code in April 2023.

In Argentina, *sarcocornia* cultivation experiences have been carried out in three different systems: Soil crops without wind protection, soil crops in tunnels and greenhouse crops. The productive cycle begins mid-December when the plant matures. At this time, shoots (5 cm in length) are collected using cuttings or stolons, transplanted, and watered with seawater (11 to 20 g/L) in a greenhouse at 20°C. It is harvested after four months of growth until reaching lengths of 13 cm. This type of harvest with staggered cuts makes it possible to lengthen the phenological cycle of the species and obtain sprouts through vegetative reproduction for the second year of production, resulting in a cycle of 120 days from the capture of shoots to harvest.

Productive cycle of *S. magellanica* developed in greenhouse. © CADIC-CONICET.

5.1.3 Whitebait – *Sarcocornia* IMTA

There are many examples of using halophytes as biofilters to treat final effluents from marine aquaculture, and, in recent years, these have begun to be used as components of integrated multitrophic systems.

The large volumes of wastewater discharged from open land-based systems can affect seriously the surrounding coast by increasing nutrients, mainly inorganic N and P. An option successfully applied for disposing of marine aquaculture effluent is using salt-tolerant plants commonly named halophytes. These species have great potential for reducing and recycling waste, optimizing resource utilization, and developing alternative production in the frame of a sustainable model for a circular economy. Constructed wetlands could be a good option for treating and/or exploiting wastewater in a highly cost-efficient way, requiring low investment. Besides, this system avoids or diminishes the necessity of using plastic. This system has the limitation that wastewater availability from seafood processing plants is not constant throughout the year since it is interrupted during closed seasons. A strategy to overcome this limitation could be to incorporate water used for whitebait production into *sarcocornia* cultivation. Particularly, since *sarcocornia* cuttings in a greenhouse can be produced in aquaponic cultures, this system could be temporarily coupled with the production of puyen as a source of water rich in nitrogen and inorganic dissolved phosphorus. The latter would be beneficial in maintaining whitebait adults and larvae since both phases grow in euryhaline environments.

5.1.4 Blue Mussel (*Mytilus chilensis*)

Blue Mussel (*Mytilus chilensis*)

The blue mussel *Mytilus chilensis* is a filter-feeder bivalve that is distributed along the Pacific coast of Chile and up to Brazil in the Atlantic Ocean. They occur mainly in the intertidal and subtidal zone at depths of ~10m and exceptionally to 25 m. It can form dense banks of up to 5000 individuals/m² when not exposed to the breaking waves. *Mytilus chilensis* has separate sexes and a complex life cycle alternating between a planktonic larval phase and a benthic juvenile-adult phase. *M. chilensis* attains sexual maturity during its first year of life, usually in spring-summer time.

Mussel culture is well-established and occurs in many countries worldwide. The global production of *Mytilus chilensis* is up to 365.6 thousand tonnes. In 2020, the leading buyer markets for Chile's products were Spain, Russia, the United States of America, France and Italy. Global mussel aquaculture production has increased steadily since the 1950s, reaching 2 million tonnes in 2019 (FAO 2020). Nevertheless, European production has decreased while the market has increased, which is a good opportunity to boost production in other countries like Argentina to supply this market. China is the world's leading producer of mussels, while Chile is currently the second, reaching landings of 400,604 tons in 2020¹³, becoming one of the leading world exporters.

The blue mussel production cycle in the Beagle Channel lasts from 12 to 18 months from seed catchment to achieve a commercial size of 57 mm. It typically involves five steps: 1) seed catchment (2-3 cm seeds); 2) seed string when seeds are included in a cotton sleeve surrounded by a fishing net; 3) growth when cords are placed in rafts or longlines until reaching the commercial size (6-8 cm); 4) thinning when mussel density is controlled to ensure homogenous growth and avoid detachments; and 5) harvest when the mussels are detached, cleaned, and size graded for commercialisation. The

¹³ SERNAPESCA (2020). Anuarios estadísticos de pesca y acuicultura 2020. <http://www.sernapesca.cl/informacion-utilidad/anuarios-estadisticos-de-pesca-y-acuicultura>

seed collectors are installed one month after the spawning season to ensure the settlement of the post-larvae in December-February. Since the mussel production cycle begins with the collection of natural seeds, conducting studies on the state and distribution of natural banks would be advisable.

Typical productive cycle of blue mussel in the Beagle Channel. © CADIC-CONICET.

5.1.5 Red Sea Urchin (*Loxechinus albus*)

Red Sea Urchin (*Loxechinus albus*)

Loxechinus albus has a wide geographic distribution in the south-eastern Pacific Ocean. It is found uninterruptedly from the north of Peru (6°53'50" S) to the southern tip of the American continent (57°58'00" S). The red sea urchin is a member of the phylum Echinodermata, which contains about six thousand species, including starfish and sea cucumbers. This species inhabits mainly rocky bottoms and *Macrocystis* forests, feeding on algae. Its maximum size can reach 150 mm in diameter without considering the spines.

Sea urchin roe is considered a delicacy worldwide and is a traditional food in Japan, a country that accounts for over 80 % of the global consumption of this seafood. Consumer demand for sea urchins is driven by several key market factors, including innovation, experimentation, and health. The organoleptic characteristics of sea urchins' gonads (size and colour, among others) determine the final market value. High-value products for niche and luxury markets around sea urchins have been detected as an internal strength, with great economic opportunities due to sea urchins' consumption booms in Asian markets. As a social external factor, sea urchins require valorisation as a viable product to achieve new markets.

Loxechinus albus is one of the most economically important species for the artisanal fishery in the Pacific littoral benthic of South America, and Chile has one of the most important sea urchin fisheries worldwide. Chilean landings of *L. albus* averaged 18,077 tons between 2010 and 2016, causing a dramatic decrease in population density and alterations in size structure. Due to the increased demand

for sea urchins as human food, and because landings have fallen by more than half in the last 20 years, aquaculture of this species is in full expansion.

Some knowledge has been accumulated to enable the cultivation of larvae and juveniles of *L. albus* in a controlled environment. From a list of 17 echinoderm species from Latin America with commercial value, the sea cucumber *Isostichopus fuscus*, and the sea urchins, *L. albus* and *Arbacia dufresnii* stand out for their potential for aquaculture. This list is supported by growth, feed conversion, nutritional and nutraceutical values, domestication grade, and relevance for re-stocking wild populations¹⁴. Aquaculture research on red sea urchins has focused mainly on the reproductive cycle and larval production for repopulation and gonadal improvement through the implementation of artificial diets. High gonadal production by feeding with artificial diets has been reported for *L. albus*. One of the main bottleneck for culture of this species is the long period required to achieve market size.

The systems experimented with for the growth of red sea urchins have been land-based open systems using rectangular or conical fiberglass tanks and open systems in cages suspended or supported on the marine bed. The productive cycle of *L. albus* begins with the capture of adult individuals by diving before the spawning season. Once in the laboratory, they are induced to spawn by injecting in the coelomic cavity with 3 ml of 0.5 M KCl through the peristomial membrane. Fertilization takes place in 50-l plastic containers 4.5 X10⁶ eggs/container, stirring gently, add 10 ml of sperm suspension, prepared by diluting 1 ml of concentrated sperm from five adult male urchins in 200 ml seawater. From there, they are attached to suspended culture systems or through cages on rocky bottoms, to which maintenance must be carried out and food renewed by diving.

¹⁴ Sonnenholzner-Varas JI (2021). ¿Hacia dónde va la acuicultura de equinodermos en América Latina? Potencial, retos y oportunidades. Revista de Biología Tropical, 69:514-549

Productive cycle of red sea urchin. © CADIC-CONICET.

One option for the first commercial steps in developing sea urchin farming is to supply the local market around international tourism that is growing in the province of Tierra del Fuego. *Loxechinus albus* is not included in the Argentine Food Code. Nevertheless, *A. dufresnii* is the first and only echinoderm included, which would facilitate the incorporation of new species. As was mentioned for whitebait, it is suggested that when marketing the product, it should be highlighted that it comes from local aquaculture, which could increase consumer confidence and add value.

5.1.6 Blue Mussel - Red Sea Urchin IMTA

As mentioned, one of the drawbacks of blue mussel cultivation in longlines is the overloading of lines due to biofouling, for which various preventive solutions and treatments have been sought. A novel opportunity that arises from IMTA systems is the possibility of biologically controlling biofouling by integrating the production of species that take advantage of biofouling as food. Furthermore, sea urchins grown on longlines deployed higher survival and growth rates than wild stocks.

The main limitation to developing profitable urchin aquaculture is their low growth rate, requiring five years to reach adult size. A possible strategy to develop a more cost-effective activity is to cultivate adult sea urchins starting from wild individuals with the sole objective of improving their gonad index, avoiding the previous growth stage.

6 Potential for IMTA in Nigeria

Aquaculture is one of the fastest growing agricultural food production sectors in Nigeria. It involves the cultivation of aquatic organisms (animals and plants) in fresh, brackish or sea waters.

In Nigeria, aquaculture practice began in 1951, with an experimental station at Onikan Lagos and the Panyam Industrial Fish Farm in Jos, Plateau State, established by the Federal Government of Nigeria^{15,16}. In 2000, fish from aquaculture contributed about 0.15% to Nigeria's GDP, and by 2014 about 0.48% reflecting the fact that the sector has been growing at a rate of around 20% per year since 2003¹⁷. Aquaculture in Nigeria revolves around catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) farming¹⁸, which accounts for more than 80% of the total farmed species from aquaculture¹⁹. Other commonly cultured fish species in Nigeria include *Heterobranchus* spp. (catfish), *Tilapia* spp. (*Tilapia*), *Cyprinus carpio* (Common carp), *Heterotis niloticus* (African bonytongue)²⁰. The production of farmed fish is largely based on small-scale operations ranging from homestead concrete ponds of 25-40m to small earthen ponds of 0.02 ha^{11, 21}.

In Nigeria fish is one of the main sources of animal protein. Fish can be obtained in Nigeria either by capture fisheries, fish aquaculture or importation of frozen fish. According to FAO, protein intake in poor nations was lower than the recommended 75g per person per day²².

Nigeria has abundant fresh, brackish and sea water with the potential to boost fish protein security, alleviate poverty and increase its GDP through aquaculture. Over the years, the Nigerian Institute for Oceanography and Marine Research (NIOMR) has carried out research on the culture of various species of finfish and shellfish in Nigeria.

The various species can be seen in table below:

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- ¹⁵ Olagunju, F. I., Adesiyun, I. O., and Ezekiel, A. A. (2007). Economic viability of catfish production in Oyo state, Nigeria. *Journal of Human Ecology*, **21**(2): 121-124. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09709274.2007.11905961>.
- ¹⁶ Adewumi, A. A. (2015). Aquaculture in Nigeria: Sustainability issues and challenges. *Direct Research Journal of Agriculture and Food Science*, **3**(12): 223-231.
- ¹⁷ Ozigbo, E., Anyadike, C., Adegbite, O. and Kolawole P. (2014). Review of Aquaculture Production and Management in Nigeria. *American Journal of Experimental Agriculture*, **4**(10): 1137-1151.
- ¹⁸ Adewumi, A. A. and Olaleye, V. F. (2011). Catfish culture in Nigeria: Progress, prospects and problems. *African journal of agriculture research*. **6**(6): 1281-1283.
- ¹⁹ Atanda, A. N. (2007). Freshwater fish seed resources in Nigeria. In Bondad-Reantaso M.G. (Ed.), *Assessment of freshwater fish seed resources for sustainable aquaculture* (pp. 361-380). Food and Agriculture Org.
- ²⁰ Omeje, J. E., Sule, A. M., and Aguihe, E. O. (2020). An assessment of aquaculture table-size fish farmers activities in Kainji Lake Basin, Nigeria. *Agro-Science*, **19**(2), 36-40.
- ²¹ Oluwasola, O. & Ige, A. O. (2015). Factors Determining the profitability of catfish production in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. *Sustainable Agriculture Research*, Canadian Center of Science and Education, **4**(4). <https://doi.org/10.22004/ag.econ.230365>.
- ²² Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (2020). *The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2020. Sustainability in action*. Rome. <https://doi.org/10.4060/ca9229en>

Finfish and Shellfish Cultures in NIOMR

Common name	Latin name	Habitat	Role in IMTA	Culture Status
Finfish				
African catfish	<i>Clarias gariepinus</i>	Freshwater	Fed species	Breed to table size
African catfish	<i>Heterobranchus bidorsalis</i>	Freshwater	Fed species	Breed to table size
African catfish	<i>Heterobranchus longifilis</i>	Freshwater	Fed species	Breed to table size
Hybrid catfish	Heteroclarias	Freshwater	Fed species	Breed to table size
Nile Tilapia	<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	Freshwater	Fed species	Breed to table size
Guinean Tilapia	<i>Tilapia guineensis</i>	Brackish water	Fed species	Breed to table size
Black chin		Brackish water	Fed species	Growth trials
Common carp		Freshwater	Fed species	To be cultured
Mullet		Euryhaline	Fed species	Feeding trials
Red snapper		Marine & Brackish	Fed species	Breeding & Growth trials
Bagrid catfish	<i>Chrysichthys nigrodigitatus</i>	Euryhaline	Fed species	Breeding & Growth trials
Megalops		Euryhaline	Fed species	Growth trials
Snake head		Freshwater	Fed species	Growth trials
Nile Arowana	<i>Heterotis niloticus</i>	Freshwater	Fed species	Growth trials
Cassava Croaker	Pseudolithus	Marine	Fed species	Potential species
Grouper		Marine	Fed species	Potential species
Shellfish				
<i>Penaeus monodon</i>		Marine		Breed to table size
<i>Macrobrachium vollenhovenii</i>		Freshwater		Breeding trials

Oyster	Brackish water	Grow out trials
Integrated fish farming		
Poultry, fish and vegetable	Freshwater	Successful
Rice with fish	Freshwater	Successful
Pig and fish farming		Successful
Maggot production		Successful

6.1 Culturing

Pond System: This is the most commonly used technique in areas close to rivers or lagoons. Land is excavated to build embankments for holding water. Its closeness to the lagoon allows for the pond to be fed by the tidal flow of lagoon waters and it is controlled by means of a monk or sluice gate; harvesting is done by drag net or cast net.

Pond System of Aquaculture

Pen System: Fish pen is made up of materials which include the fence (stakes), the mesh or netting materials, floats, sinkers, line/ropes, twines and pegs. Fish pen is becoming more popular for brackish water culture because of its simple technology and management, it is similar to cage culture but with an open end. The quantity of materials depends on the size and shape of the pen. Fish grown in pen have access to benthic organisms, harvesting is done with seine net, encircling net traps or gill net.

Pen System of Aquaculture

Cage System: Cages are basically floating structures that are placed in open water within ponds, lakes, reservoirs, rivers, lagoons and oceans. Cages typically have a rigid framework, at the water surface or on all sides, with a suspended structure beneath the water surface in which the culture species are retained. The upper rigid framework is provided with floating devices to keep the upper part above water level. Cages can be of different shape such as square, rectangular or circular at the top and bottom with various depth.

Fish species reared in cages include Tarpon (*Megalops atlanticus*), Tilapia guineensis, Mulletts (*Mugil cephalus* and *liza falcipinis*).

Cage System of Aquaculture

Other culture systems include:

- Acadja System
- Concrete Tanks
- Plastic Tanks
- Fibre Glass Tanks
- Water Flow through Tanks
- Recirculatory Aquaculture Systems
- Integrated Aquaculture (Rice with Fish Culture)
- NIOMR Buguma Station Integrated Fish with Oyster Farm

Acadja System

Concrete Tanks

Plastic Tanks

Fibre Glass Tanks

Water Flow through Tanks

Recirculation Aquaculture Systems

Integrated Aquaculture (Rice with Fish Culture)

NIOMR Buguma Station Integrated Fish with Oyster Farm

6.2 Prospect of IMTA in Nigeria

Way Forward

- Capacity building.
- Public private partnerships.
- Aquaculture value chain development.
- Adoption of sustainable aquaculture practices.
- Research and innovation.

IMTA is quite a new concept in Nigeria. However, a system closely related to IMTA, which include the combination of fish culture with crop production and animal husbandry, is currently being practiced in some areas. This is an environmentally friendly aquaculture system. Integrated aquaculture in Nigeria is in the form of livestock - fish integrated systems, Crop - fish integrated systems including rice integrated with the fish system, horticulture integrated with the fish system, sericulture (silkworm production) integrated with the fish system, and mushrooms integrated with the fish system²³.

In Nigeria, IMTA is still in its infancy but presents great prospects towards becoming the aquaculture of the future. The 853 km of coastline and numerous tidal lagoons in Nigeria represent significant untapped potential for coastal and marine aquaculture. Climate-smart aquaculture models like IMTA could be what Nigerian coastal communities need to improve their livelihoods.

As traditional aquaculture practices often face challenges such as environmental degradation, disease outbreaks and inefficiency of resources, IMTA presents a promising alternative that integrates biological and economic principles to enhance productivity.

The potentials for IMTA in Nigeria could be harnessed through diversification of production, zero waste, environmental sustainability, economic viability and market access.

²³ Melaku, S., & Natarajan, P. (2019). Status of integrated aquaculture-Agriculture systems in Africa. *International Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Studies*, 7(4), 263–269.

6.3 Challenges to IMTA in Nigeria

- Workforce development.
- Understanding IMTA functionality and processes.
- Government support and regulatory framework.
- Unavailability of funds.
- Lack of stakeholder awareness.
- Lack of community acceptability.
- Inadequately skilled workforce.
- Limited access to capital.
- Lack of infrastructure.
- Limited research and extension services.
- Inadequate training and retraining of stakeholders.
- Lack of security.
- Power outages.
- Non-availability/ high cost of feed.

Way Forward

- Research and innovation.
- Capacity building.
- Adoption of adequate institutional policies.
- Private sector participation.
- Increased advocacy.